

Attitude and Vocabulary of Life Science of Residential and Non-Residential Ramakrishna Mission School Students in West Bengal

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ABSTRACT : Swami Vivekananda, one of the great educators of India envisioned our education system in old 'gurugrihavasa' type i.e. 'living with the guru' type of systems. Ramakrishna Mission, a NGO established by Vivekananda himself runs many Residential and Non-residential schools both in India and abroad to spread 'Man making and Character Building Education'. The present study was conducted to enquire the Attitude and Vocabulary of Life Science on randomly selected 200 IX standard students from Ramakrishna Mission Schools in West Bengal both in Residential and Non-residential setup through administering Attitude Scale and Vocabulary Question paper under different categorical variables. It was found that the non-residential school students significantly possess a higher positive attitude towards Life Science than residential school students but the rural students are not significantly different from the urban students in this respect. The present study also reveals that residential and urban students significantly possess a greater vocabulary in Life Science than their counterparts. Moreover there is not any significant difference in the effect of mentoring by school and mentoring by school and others in the formation of attitude towards Life Science and in the construction of vocabulary of Life Science among different Ramakrishna Mission school students.

Keywords : Attitude, Vocabulary, Residential, Non-residential, Mentoring, Secondary School Students.

Introduction

Twenty first century is the era of science and technology. Today without science and

technology we can't imagine of our life in this world. It pervades everywhere in our daily life, and among all the scientific discipline life science is most important because it deals with our

existence in this planet. In this regard ASBMB (American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology) says that “The molecular life sciences are at the forefront of scientific discovery. Over the past decade, an ever growing arsenal of techniques has helped researchers dissect the innermost secrets of the cell and develop new ways to detect and attack disease. These techniques also have been used to produce vast amounts of once rare drugs and vaccines, trace the path of evolution, create instant tests for a host of illnesses, warn people when their children might inherit a deadly disease, and identify criminals and victims of disasters.” They also add that the leaders in this scientific revolution have been biochemists and molecular biologists. “If cancer is to be cured, if solutions to the world’s energy crisis are to be found, or if the planet’s pollution is to be cleaned up, it will probably be the biochemists and molecular biologists with the knowledge and skills to power these breakthroughs.” So it is important to have interest among students in Life Science for both the reasons –to better understand and adjustment with nature and to explore new knowledge which may increase the survival of human beings in this World.

The present work is dealt with Ramakrishna Mission Schools, so it is noteworthy to discuss little about this organization and its educational activities. Here is a brief description of the educational activity of Ramakrishna Mission by Sanyal (2012), “The setting up of the Ramakrishna Math and Ramakrishna Mission wasone of the greatest contributions made by the Math and Mission to the human race in general, and Indians in particular. As on 2010, there are about 172 Mission centres, including 42 in 19 countries outside India, propagating this message. There are 1506

educational institutions of various types with more than 400,000 students benefiting as much as possible from the type of education Swamiji envisaged.”

In West Bengal Ramakrishna Mission have nearly 14 secondary schools. Swami Vivekananda envisioned our education system in old ‘*gurugrihavasas*’ type; —”The old institution of ‘living with the guru’ and similar systems of imparting education are needed. What we want are western science coupled with Vedanta, *brahmacharya* as the guiding motto, and also *sraddha* and faith in one’s own self.” So some of the Ramakrishna Mission School emerged as completely residential Boarding schools like Narendrapur, Purulia etc; and others started as non-residential schools with hostel facilities for limited number of students. It has been observed by the present researcher that the Ramakrishna Mission Boarding school campus have a variety of flora and fauna. So, it can be assumed that the students of residential schools get unique opportunity to closely observe and interact with the nature. This close and continuous interaction with nature may foster the curiosity of the learner towards this natural world which may have a direct impact on their attitude and vocabulary of Life Science. As many school teachers also stay in the school campus so it is expected that students of residential schools may interact with their teachers even after school period. Teachers also get opportunity to show their students living plant and animal specimens and their interaction directly in the natural ecosystem. Although the main purpose of this ‘living with the guru’ type of education proposed by Swami Vivekananda, is ‘man-making’ and ‘character-building’ by staying with teachers of strong ethical and moral characters; but, it can be assumed that this

variety of natural World what Boarding school campus offers to their students may have some impact in their students' vocabulary and attitude towards Life Science. Still now as there are very little attempt to search such impact on students; this present study is to reveal the impact of residential schools of Ramakrishna Mission over the non-residential type in developing vocabulary and attitude towards Life Science.

From the review of related literature it was found that, there was a good number of works on attitude and aptitude towards science but study related to science vocabulary was very scarce. Present researcher has hardly found any work directly related with the relationship between attitude and vocabulary of science. Work on the effect of residential type of schooling over students' academic achievement or attitude formation in any discipline was also very scarce. One work by Rao (1990) shows the impact of residential type of schooling over the science achievement and science attitude formation on students. There was a good number of works related to students' attitude toward science in different categorical variables. Work of Nellaippan (1992) shows that gender and locality of the students do not influence in their scientific attitude and scientific interests. In a similar type of work Malviya (1991) proves that the students who had positive attitude towards science also had greater interest in science. Kar (1990) in his study also reveals that there was positive relationship between attitude and achievement in general science of Class IX students.

Objectives of the study

O₁: To study the attitude towards Life Science of secondary level Ramakrishna

Mission school students across the location and nature of schools.

O₂: To measure the vocabulary of Life Science of secondary level Ramakrishna Mission school students across the location and nature of schools.

O₃: To compare the attitude and vocabulary of Life Science between residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission school students.

O₄: To compare the attitude and vocabulary of Life Science between rural and urban Ramakrishna Mission school students.

O₅: To find out the effect of 'mentoring by school' over 'mentoring by school and others' in the formation of attitude and vocabulary of Life Science among Ramakrishna Mission school students.

O₆: To study the relationship between attitude and vocabulary of Life Science in residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission schools.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There will be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

H₀₂: There would be no significant difference in vocabulary of Life Science between residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

H₀₃: There would be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between rural and urban Ramakrishna Mission School students.

H₀₄: There would be no significant difference in vocabulary of Life Science

between rural and urban Ramakrishna Mission School students.

H₀5: There would be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between the students under 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' of Ramakrishna Mission Schools.

H₀6: There would be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between the students under 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' Ramakrishna Mission Schools.

H₀7: There would be no significant relation between attitude towards Life Science and vocabulary of Life Science in residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Methodology

Variables:

The present research had identified two types of variables-

A) Major:

- i) Students' attitude towards Life Science
- ii) Students vocabulary of Life Science

B) Categorical:

- i) Location of school (Rural and urban)
- ii) Nature of school (Residential and non-residential)
- iii) Mentoring

Population

For this research work the population will be ninth standard school students of Govt. aided Ramakrishna Mission schools in West Bengal

under 'West Bengal Board of Secondary Education' (W.B.B.S.E.).

Sample and sampling procedure

To constitute the sample, at first, two types of schools (residential and non-residential) were purposively selected locality wise (urban and rural), among the Ramakrishna Mission schools of West Bengal. The sample was selected from the different schools of South 24 Parganas and Kolkata district. All the schools were aided by Government of West Bengal and academically controlled by West Bengal Board of Secondary Education (WBBSE). The sample has randomness in nature.

Tools of the study

Present researcher had used two types of tools; one was self made attitude scale to measure the students' attitude towards Life Science. Second was a question paper to measure the vocabulary of Life Science of ninth standard students.

Life Science attitude scale for secondary level school students

The scale was constructed by the present researcher with the help of his guide Dr. A.Guha and Sri U. Paul. The total items of the scale were 33. The categories of responses were 'strongly agree', 'agree', 'undecided', 'disagree', 'strongly disagree' and '5', '4', '3', '2', '1' were the respective scores awarded for the responses. Some items were negative in nature and the scoring was done in reverse order i.e. '1', '2', '3', '4', '5'.

Validity and Reliability of the tools

Content validity was done by two experts. The items were modified according to their

suggestions. Few items were rejected and to avoid the ambiguity of items language of few items were modified by them.

Reliability of the scale was computed by using Cronbach's Alpha through SPSS 20.0 version and was found 0.837 and it has a good alpha value and it was acceptable.

Table 1.1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
0.837	33

Life Science vocabulary question paper for ninth standard students

A question paper was developed by the researcher himself for testing the vocabulary of Life science of ninth standard students of West Bengal Board. The paper contains 25 items, each containing 1 marks so all together 25 marks. Ten fill in the blanks type, ten short answer type and five diagram leveling types. The content validity of the items of question paper was also validated by experts.

Procedure of Data collection

Data related to the attitude and vocabulary of Life Science was collected by the researcher

Table 1.2: Descriptive statistics of attitude towards Life Science

Categories	Statistic	Std. Error
Mean	130.08	.982
Median	131.00	
Variance	194.004	
Std. Deviation	13.929	
Skewness	-.358	.172
Kurtosis	.273	.341

himself, by personally visiting the Ramakrishna Mission schools.

Table 1.3: Descriptive statistics of vocabulary of Life Science

Categories	Statistic	Std. Error
Mean	16.33	.409
Median	18.00	
Variance	33.623	
Std. Deviation	5.799	
Skewness	-.529	.172
Kurtosis	-.752	.341

Analyses and Interpretation

Objective wise Analysis of Data:

Objective no.1

O₁: To study the attitude towards Life Science of secondary level Ramakrishna Mission school students across the location and nature of schools.

Table – 1.4: Group Statistics of attitude towards Life Science_location of school

Location of School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Urban	131	129.42	14.694
Rural	70	131.31	12.376
Total	201	130.08	13.929

Table – 1.5: Group Statistics of attitude towards Life Science_nature of school

Location of School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Residential	115	127.71	14.592
Non-residential	86	133.24	12.377
Total	201	130.08	13.929

While estimating the mean value of attitude towards Life Science from the data collected from Ramakrishna Mission school students, it has been found to be 130.365 and the standard deviation value is 13.929 (table: 1.4 and 1.5). In attitude towards Life Science scale the scores may range between 33 through 99 to 165. So, it can be said that, Ramakrishna Mission school students of West Bengal possess moderate positive attitude towards Life Science.

Objective no.2

Table – 1.6: Group Statistics of vocabulary of Life Science_location of school

Location of School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Urban	131	19.66	3.350
Rural	70	10.10	3.979
Total	201	16.33	5.799

O₂: To measure the vocabulary of Life science of the secondary level Ramakrishna Mission school students across the location and nature of schools.

While measuring the vocabulary of Life Science of the students of Ramakrishna Mission schools, the score received through vocabulary test in Life Science it was found that the mean score was 16.33 out of 25 marks, and the standard deviation value was 5.799 (table: 1.6 and 1.7).

Table – 1.7: Group Statistics of vocabulary of Life Science_nature of school

Location of School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Residential	115	17.03	5.846
Non-residential	86	15.40	5.632
Total	201	16.33	5.799

Objective no.3

O₃: To compare the attitude and vocabulary of Life Science between residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission school students.

To fulfil this objective, two null hypotheses were formulated and tested which were as follows:

H₀1: There will be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

H₀2: There would be no significant difference in vocabulary of Life Science between residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Testing of Null Hypotheses:

Testing of H₀1

H₀1: There will be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Interpretation

From the analysis in Table 1.8 it is seen that in case of comparing students' attitude towards Life Science between residential and non-residential schools the calculated $t_{(199)}$ value is -2.834 and 'p' value is 0.005 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, 't' is significant at 0.05 level. So, **H₀1** is rejected and it can be safely said that residential Ramakrishna Mission School students are significantly different from non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students with respect to their attitude towards Life Science.

Table – 1.8: Group Statistics and Independent samples test of attitude towards Life Science_ residential vs. non-residential

Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Nature of school	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
residential	115	127.71	14.592	1.361	199	-2.834*	.005
non-residential	86	133.24	12.377	1.335			

(*significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Testing of H₀2

H₀2: There would be no significant difference in vocabulary of Life Science between residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Interpretation

From the analysis in Table 1.9 it is seen that in case of comparing students' attitude towards Life Science between residential and non-residential schools the calculated $t_{(199)}$ value is 1.998 and 'p' value is .047 ($p < .05$). Hence, 't' is significant at 0.05 level. So, **H₀2** is rejected and it can be safely said that residential Ramakrishna Mission School students are significantly different from non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students in their vocabulary of Life Science.

Objective no.4

O₄: To compare the attitude and vocabulary of Life Science between rural and urban Ramakrishna Mission school students.

To fulfil this objective, two null hypotheses were formulated and tested which were as follows:

H₀3: There would be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between rural and urban Ramakrishna Mission School students.

H₀4: There would be no significant difference in vocabulary of Life Science between rural and urban Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Testing of Ho3

H₀3: There would be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science

Table – 1.9: Group Statistics and Independent samples test of vocabulary of Life Science_ residential vs. non-residential

Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Nature of school	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
residential	115	17.03	5.846	0.545	199	1.998*	.047
non-residential	86	15.40	5.632	0.607			

(*significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Table – 1.10: Group Statistics and Independent samples test of attitude towards Life Science_ urban vs. rural

Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Nature of school	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Urban	131	129.42	14.694	1.284	199	-.918**	.360
Rural	70	131.31	12.376	1.479			

(**not significant at 0.05 level of significance)

between rural and urban Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Interpretation

From the analysis in Table 1.10 it is seen that in case of comparing students' attitude towards Life Science between urban and rural Ramakrishna Mission schools the calculated $t_{(199)}$ value is -0.918 and 'p' value is 0.360 ($p > 0.05$). Hence, 't' is not significant at 0.05 level. So, H_03 is accepted and it can be safely said that urban Ramakrishna Mission School students are not significantly different from rural Ramakrishna Mission School students in respect to their attitude towards Life Science.

Testing of Ho4

H_04 : There would be no significant difference in vocabulary of Life Science between rural and urban Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Interpretation

From the analysis in Table 1.11 it is seen that in case of comparing students' vocabulary of Life Science between urban and rural Ramakrishna Mission schools the calculated $t_{(199)}$ value is 18.041 and 'p' value is 0.000 ($p < .05$). Hence, 't' is significant at 0.05 level. So, H_04 is rejected and it can be safely said that urban Ramakrishna Mission School students are significantly different from rural Ramakrishna Mission School students in respect to their vocabulary of Life Science.

Objective no.5

O_6 : To find out the effect of 'mentoring by school' over 'mentoring by school and others' in the attitude and vocabulary of Life Science among Ramakrishna Mission school students.

To fulfil this objective, two null hypotheses

Table – 1.11: Group Statistics and Independent samples test of vocabulary of Life Science_ urban vs. rural

Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Nature of school	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Urban	131	19.66	3.350	.293	199	18.041*	.000
Rural	70	10.10	3.979	.476			

(*significant at 0.05 level of significance)

were formulated and tested which were as follows:

H₀5: There would be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between the students under 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' of Ramakrishna Mission School.

H₀6: There would be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between the students under 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' Ramakrishna Mission School.

Testing of Ho7

H₀5: There would be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between the students under 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' of Ramakrishna Mission School.

Interpretation

From the analysis in Table 1.12 it is seen that in case of comparing students' attitude towards Life Science between 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' the calculated $t_{(199)}$ value is -0.799 and 'p' value is 0.425 ($p > 0.05$). Hence, 't' is not significant at 0.05 level. So, **H₀5** is not rejected and it can be safely said that there exist no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Testing of H₀6

H₀6: There would be no significant difference in attitude towards Life Science between the students under 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' Ramakrishna Mission School.

Table – 1.12: Group Statistics and Independent samples test of attitude towards Life Science_ mentoring by school vs. mentoring by school and others

Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Mentoring	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
only school	100	129.29	13.925	1.392	199	-0.799**	0.425
school with others	101	130.86	13.957	1.389			

(**not significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Table - 1.13: Group Statistics and Independent samples test of vocabulary in Life Science_ mentoring by school vs. mentoring by school and others

Group Statistics					t-test for Equality of Means		
Mentoring	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
only school	100	16.09	6.027	.603	199	-0.591**	0.555
school with others	101	16.57	5.583	.556			

(**not significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation

From the analysis in Table 1.13 it is seen that in case of comparing students' vocabulary of Life Science between 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' the calculated $t_{(199)}$ value is -0.591 and 'p' value is 0.555 ($p > 0.05$). Hence, 't' is not significant at 0.05 level. So, H_06 is not rejected and it can be safely said that there exist no significant difference in vocabulary of Life Science between 'mentoring by school' and 'mentoring by school and others' Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Objective no.6

O6: To study the relationship between attitude and vocabulary of Life Science in residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission schools.

To fulfil this objective, one null hypothesis was formulated and tested which was as follows:

H₀₇: There would be no significant relation between attitude towards Life Science and vocabulary of Life Science in residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Testing of H₀₇

H₀₇: There would be no significant relation between attitude towards Life Science and vocabulary of Life Science in residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Interpretation

The analysis in table 1.14 shows that, correlation coefficient i.e. 'r' between score of attitude towards life science and vocabulary in life science is 0.053 and p value is 0.458 ($p > 0.05$) which is not significant at the 0.05 level. Hence, H_07 is not rejected. So, it can be interpreted that there exist insignificant very low positive correlation between attitude towards Life Science and vocabulary of Life Science in residential and non-residential Ramakrishna Mission School students.

Discussions

While to search and compare the attitude towards Life Science among Ramakrishna Mission school students of West Bengal (W.B.) under different categorical variables it has been found from the study that secondary school

Table - 1.14: Correlations_ attitude and vocabulary of Life Science attitude towards Life Science vocabulary in Life Science

		Attitude towards Life Science	Vocabulary in Life Science
Attitude towards Life Science	Pearson Correlation	1	.053**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.458
	N	201	201
Vocabulary in Life Science	Pearson Correlation	.053**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.458	
	N	201	201

(**not significant at 0.05 level of significance)

students of West Bengal Ramakrishna Mission Schools possess a moderate positive attitude towards Life Science. Both the work of Malviya (1991) and Mandila's (1988) support this result that secondary level students had favorable attitude towards science.

While finding the difference of attitude towards Life Science between non-residential and residential school type it was found that non-residential school students significantly possess a higher positive attitude towards Life Science than residential school students. Rao, (1990) performed similar type of work and the result yield from his study was opposite to my study that is, students from residential schools had a higher attitude towards science than the non-residential school students.

While comparing the attitude towards Life Science it was found that rural students are not significantly different from the urban students. Nellaippan's (1992) work also support this findings although Rao's (1990) work reveals that rural students have better attitude towards biology than urban students.

The present study also implies that residential students significantly possess a greater vocabulary in Life Science than the non-residential students among Ramakrishna Mission Schools. Rao (1990) worked on achievement of biology among secondary school students and his study also support this findings that residential students possess better vocabulary of Life Science than their counter parts.

In this present work it was found that urban students significantly possess a greater vocabulary in Life Science than the rural students among Ramakrishna Mission Schools. Mandila

(1988) performed similar kind of work and the result of his study supports this finding that urban students have better vocabulary of science than rural students.

The present study also reveals that there is not any significant difference in the effect of mentoring by school and mentoring by school and others in the formation of attitude towards Life Science and in the construction of vocabulary of Life Science among different Ramakrishna Mission school students. Although, such type of works by other researchers was not found by the present researcher, Malviya's (1991) study reveals that socio-economic status of students have not any effect on students' science attitude formation.

It was found in this study that students' attitude towards Life Science is scarcely and positively correlated with their vocabulary of that subject; although this relation is statistically insignificant. This means if the students' attitude towards Life Science is increased then their vocabulary of the subject will be also increased and vice-versa but this result is due to chance as the correlation value is very low and insignificant. Darchingpui (1989), Kar (1990), Rao (1990) and Akpýnar et al (2009) also found that there exist a positive correlation between scientific attitude and achievement.

Conclusion

It is evident from this work that residential type of schooling or in Swami Vivekananda's word 'gurugrihavasas' type of education, where both the teacher and taught are residing in the same campus; in secondary level have a significant influence in the formation of Life Science vocabulary among the students; along

with its main objectives 'man-making and character-building education' of the students. Although in this present study it was found that attitude towards Life Science was higher among the non-residential type in comparison to residential type, it seems that other factors like parents' aspiration, Life Science teachers' role, students' carrier concern, students' socio-economic background may be involved here in their attitude formation which paves way for further research.

The study also reveals that, although locations of school have not any significant influence in students' attitude towards Life Science development; it had been observed that location of school had a substantial role in the students' vocabulary of Life Science formation. We found urban students with a higher vocabulary of Life Science to their counterparts. Students' intelligence, socio-economic background etc. might be involved here which also gives way for further research.

The present study also reveals that there is not any significant difference in the effect of mentoring by school and mentoring by school and others in the formation of attitude towards Life Science and in the construction of vocabulary of Life Science among different Ramakrishna Mission school students. This result has a particular significance in the contemporary Indian educational scenario where guardians feel that without private tuition it is impossible to excel in school subjects by their children. The result clearly shows that monitoring other than school has no influence in attitude and vocabulary formation in Life Science among Ramakrishna Mission school students.

Limitations of the study

Studies related to humanities are not always flawless. This present study had some limitations which were as follows:

- i. The study was limited only among the Ramakrishna Mission Schools.
- ii. For reviewing of the related literature, the books and journals were consulted as far as possible but help of internet was not done at its utmost level.
- iii. The school selection for this study was not done with strict randomization.
- iv. The schools were selected mainly from southern part of West Bengal.
- v. The numbers of schools were only four; it might be increased by taking more schools under the study.
- vi. The sample of this study was selected only from the Govt. aided Bengali medium schools of WBBSE run by the Ramakrishna Mission authorities. It would be much better if the sample could be selected from other Govt., Govt. aided and English medium schools of WBBSE board.

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